

TYPOLOGICAL ANALYZES OF GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES OF NUMBERS AND CASES IN HINDI AND UZBEK

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7389038>

PhD **Rahmatjonova Kamola Abdumutal qizi**

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

+99890 947 41 23

E-mail: rakhmatjanova@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

Comparing the two languages, a new stage emerges not only in Hindi and Uzbek linguistics, but also in world linguistics. Because is easier to learn and teach the language. The present study considers of the grammatical representation of the category of number of two genetically and typological different languages Hindi and Uzbek. There are authentic material for illustration-studied items taken from modern fictions of the Hindi and Uzbek authors. Affinities and differences in the category of number of the two languages are considers in structural, semantics and function.

Key words: *grammatical category, morphological category, Sanskrit, Hindi, Indo-Aryan languages, Latin.*

We know Hindi as the official language of India. About 400 million people in the world speak Hindi and 120 million have Hindi as their second language. It has been strongly influenced by Sanskrit; a lot of words in Hindi come from there. There are numerous other facts about Hindi that most of you wouldn't know.

The sentence structure in Hindi differs widely from English. In Hindi verbs and auxiliary verbs always go to the end of the sentence. For instance, the sentence, आप कैसे हैं in Hindi actually translates to 'How are you?' in English; but if the word to word translation is considered, the sentence becomes 'You how are'. Similarly, मैं अच्छा हूँ, becomes *I fine am* instead of *I am fine*. However, although genetically and morphologically quite different, the structure of sentence in Hindi is similar to that in Uzbek. For example, मैं अध्यापक हूँ | in Hindi; *Men o'qituvchiman (I am a teacher)* in Uzbek.

The aim of the topic is to make a contrastive - typological analysis of the grammatical categories number and case of noun in the Hindi and Uzbek languages.

Grammatical category – the system of form, which have unique meaning. Usually grammatical category has two types: morphological and syntactic grammatical category.

Such kind of a method does not exist in many languages. Despite some classical Indo-Aryan languages, such as Latin, Sanskrit and etc., in Indian language category of case is not syntax, but morphological class.³

Morphologic grammatical category – the system of two and more meanings and forms of these meanings, which can be, composed one with another. For example, the categories of tense of verb and nouns.³

Syntax grammatical category – form that serve to show the syntax relation by uniting the word by their meanings. For example, the category of case.³

In the grammatical system of all languages, the category of case takes very important place. The relation of subject with other words depends on the category of case. This category “is a system of forms that shows the relation and addition of subject to other subject or verb”.³

The category of case shows the feature of the language. This feature helps to indicate the meaning of the word and to explore the language itself if one considers carefully it shows the importance of the topic.

The object of the topic is number and case grammatical categories of the noun used in the authentic texts of Hindi and Uzbek languages.

The scientific novelty of the topic: the grammatical categories of number and case of the noun Hindi and Uzbek languages were studied for the first time within the contrastive - typological aspects, as a result, general and specify features of selected languages was determined linguistic facts of converging, relatively converging and divergent languages of Hindi and Uzbek is founded;

In both languages, the commonality of the number grammatical category in terms of meaning and functions determined based on authentic materials;

The similarities and differences between the two comparable languages were analyzed on the example of the agreement category, and the actual results of the analyzes are reflected in the tables.

This topic is one of the first scientific researches in Uzbekistan, devoted to the comparative typological study of the Hindi and Uzbek languages, belonging to two different families, the Indo-Aryan language group of the Indo-European language family and the Turkic language group of the Altaic language family respectively.

At present, one of the most pressing issues in the study of different languages in the partial realm of world linguistics is the comparative study of two languages in a typological way. In addition, the present study focuses on foreign language problems - learning and comprehending - especially for the purpose of comparison of the different grammatical genres of the native language - Uzbek - remains an important task.

The purpose of the present study is to analyze the grammatical categories of nouns in Hindi and Uzbek languages based on a typological approach.

Based on above, grammatical categories are divided into types such as morphological and syntactic categories. A grammatical category in any language can be included in a group of grammatical categories only based on the internal nature of the language. A grammatical category that is morphologically considered in one language (e.g., a grammatical category specific to a noun in Uzbek) may be a syntactic category in another language.

In addition, it was found that in the Hindi language, noun-specific numbers and conjunctions fall into the morphological-syntactic grammatical categories. Moreover, in this language, the number is related to morphological and syntactic grammatical categories. For example,

	Grammatical categories of Noun	Hindi	Uzbek
.	Gender	morphological grammatical category	-
.	Number	syntactic grammatical category	morphological grammatical category
.	Case	syntactic grammatical category	syntactic grammatical category
.	Possessive category	-	syntactic grammatical category
.	Definiteness	-	-

Therefore, there are three grammatical categories (gender, number and case) of Noun in Hindi⁴ and there are three grammatical categories (possessive, number and case) of Noun in Uzbek¹.

The peculiarity of the grammatical category of numbers in the Hindi and Uzbek languages is the phenomenon of mutual isomorphism. In these languages, the singular form of nouns is equal to the morpheme \emptyset , that is, no pointer is involved to express the meaning of the singular.

In the following analyzes, partial and complete isomorphism of the grammatical category of numbers in the selected languages were observed in all three groups. In both languages, plural affixes (in Hindi -याँ, -एँ, -ए, while in Uzbek -lar (-s), a) do not occur because of the semantic nature of the base to which it is added. For example,

In Hindi:

1. भोला ने आँखें कुछ ऐसी फेरीं कि उसे अब रघू में सब बुराइयाँ ही बुराइयाँ नज़र आती ।⁶
2. मेरे पुराने दोस्त हैं ।
3. नवीन जी की आँखें सजल हो गई ।⁷

In Uzbek:

1. U ham osmonga – xira yulduzlarga qaradi. (He also looked at the sky – the opaque stars.)⁸
2. Martning oxirgi kunlari edi. (It was the last days of March)
3. Osmonda suzib yurgan bulut parchalari oftobni bir zumda yuz kuyga solayapti.⁸ (Pieces of clouds floating in the sky instantly put the sun in a different state).

In addition, it is expressed with numeral words of number grammatical category of Noun in these languages.

In Hindi:

1. पन्ना के चार बच्चे थे तीन बेटे और एक बेटा ।⁷
2. छः महीने बाद वह कलकत्ता से घर आया ।⁶
3. एक महीना गुज़र गया ।

In Uzbek:

1. Bir kun o'tdi, uch kun o'tdi, o'n kun o'tdi, na Salimjon, na qudalar, hech kim yo'lamadi.⁸ (One day passed, three days passed, ten days passed neither Salimjon, nor the relatives, nor anyone came)
2. Bir qop somon, o'n o'n beshta xoda, bir arava qamish – uy, ho'kiz topish uchun necha zamonlar qozonni suvga tashlab qo'yish kerak bo'ladi.⁸ (A pair of

straw, fifteen stalks, a card reed – to find a house and bull will need put only water in the pot for some time).

3. *Uch-to'rt kishi bo'lib asta kirsak, hovlining o'rtasida katta gulhan, hotini Malohatxon uning atrofida dodlab yuribdi.*⁸ (When we slowly entered in *groups of three or four*, there was a big fire in the middle of the yard, and his wife Malohatkhan was screaming around him.)

It may be noticed that in case of number + noun, there are different rules even in one language family. For example, in Hindi, we see if the number-qualifying noun is more than one, noun will be also plural. Like चार बच्चे *char bachche*, but in Persian, also from Indo-Aryan family of Indo-European family, qualifying noun will remain singular like Uzbek.

Although the types of case in Hindi and Uzbek differ in number (8 in Hindi and 6 in Uzbek), some agreements are found to be similar in meaning. In particular, words that come in the forms of subject, object (*tushum*), adverb of place and time, and exit are in the phenomenon of isomorphism due to their multifunctional nature. Although agglutinative traits predominate in one of the selected languages analytically, it has been observed that the functional structure of the consonant forms in the sentence is in most cases the same. For example,

	कारक	विभक्ति	In Uzbek
.	कर्ता	Ø, ने	Ø
.	करण	को	-ni
.	कर्म	से, के द्वारा	bilan, yordamida
.	सम्प्रदान	के लिए, को	uchun, -ga, -ka, -qa
.	अपादान	से	-dan
.	सम्बन्ध	का, के, की,	-ning
.	अधिकरण	में, पर	-da
.	संबोधन	हे, अरे	hoy, iya

--	--	--	--

In Hindi:

मुलिया का जीवन अंधकारमय हो गया ।⁶

मेरे लिए दुनिया में कोई देवता नहीं कोई गुरु नहीं कोई हाकिम नहीं।⁶

उसके मुख पर उल्लास था और आँखों में गर्व।⁶

In Uzbek:

*Qozonning zangi chiqib qoraygan go'jaga qatiq ham rang kirgizolmadi.*⁸ (Milk couldn't add white color to the food in the *blackened dish*).

Uning yuzida xiralik va ko'zlarida g'urur bor edi. (There was sadness *on his face* and pride *in his eyes*).

In general, linguistics, the theoretical and practical study of a particular language has a number of problems, such as the systemic structure of language, its close connection with historical processes, the movement of language and speech units as a means of communication, which is one of the most pressing problems of both theoretical and practical linguistics.

It is found out only few important cases of both the said languages is analyzed though both have many more imminent as well as complex problems to be analyzed which may be taken up by the present researcher in future. The comparative study of the discussed cases and referred have roots in historical linguistics in the development of both the languages. The outcome of the present comparative study may bring forth the close affinity in both the languages despite the fact both belong to different language families. A number of pressing issues in the field of Hindi will inevitably be studied in a comparative aspect in future research. In brief, the migration and assimilation process expanded the word corpus and absorbed with the convenient changes syntactically.

REFERENCES

1. Abdurahmonov G'. O'zbek tili grammatikasi. – T.: O'qituvchi, 1996.
2. Shomatov O.N. Hindiy tili me'yoriy grammatikasi. 1-qism. – T.: Toshkent davlat sharqshunoslik instituti, 2010. – B. 112.
3. Hojiyev A. Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug'ati. –T.: “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2002.
4. Bholana:th Tiva:ri – Hindi: bha:sha: – Ila:ha:ba:d, 1972. – P. 709.

5. Va:sudevanandan Prasa:d – A:dhunik hindi: vya:karaN oar rachna: – Bha:rti: bhavan, PaTna:, 2003. – P. 406.

Examples for illustration are taken from:

6. Premchand – Ma:nasrovar – 1, Dilli: – P. 280.
7. Premchand – Ma:nasrovar – 2, Dilli:– P. 304.
8. Abdulla Qahhor. Dahshat. – T.: Adabiyot uchqunlari, 2018. – B. 109.
9. O'tkir Xoshimov. Ikki eshik orasi. – T.: G'. G'ilom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti – B. 109.